

Article

Exploring the Impact of Startup Businesses on Entrepreneurship and Economic Development in Nepal

Nisita Nepal

¹School of Business, Sichuan University, China

Abstract: The purpose of this article is to discuss the impact of startups on entrepreneurial and economic development in Nepal. In order to investigate the state of entrepreneurship and economic development in Nepal, the study looks into reports and studies and analyzes data from different sources, including academic research and industry statistics. With the use of this technique, the author was able to recognize trends, obstacles, and possibilities in the startup ecosystem. The author investigates the challenges that Nepalese entrepreneurs face, as well as the role that startups can play in addressing these challenges. In order to improve Nepal's startup ecosystem, the article emphasizes the significance of government support, infrastructure development, human capital development etc. The author contends that by addressing these issues, Nepal may realize its enormous potential and establish itself as a center for innovation and entrepreneurship. In order to promote economic growth and open up new prospects for young people, the article emphasizes the efforts being made by the government and other organizations to foster an atmosphere that is more welcoming to entrepreneurs. The article mainly focused on suggestions for building a thriving startup ecosystem in Nepal by making supportive policies, developing infrastructure and resources, skills development, funding etc. The government may play a huge role in supporting entrepreneurship by providing financial aid, tax advantages, and a supportive regulatory environment. However, the startups have a positive impact on the growth of entrepreneurship and economic development in Nepal and emphasize the need for ongoing support and investment in the nation's entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Keywords: Startup; Entrepreneurship; Development; Business; Economy

*Corresponding Author

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Introduction

Overview of Entrepreneurship in Nepal.

Located between India and China, Nepal is a small country with a potential to be an entrepreneur. However, it is yet to be explored fully due to the poor government's policies and the lack of sufficient resources to support the business

environment. Besides the lack of skilled and qualified workforce, the country also has a challenging business environment. Nepal is a developing nation with a remittance-dependent economy. Over the past few years, the country has grown its output in the technological sectors of tourism and hydropower, as well as in the production of electricity. The majority of Nepal's youth depart the country to work in a variety of foreign nations, and remittances have a big impact on the economy of the nation. Dissatisfied young people in Nepal frequently say, "There are no opportunities in Nepal." The seemingly never-ending line at the Department of Passports demonstrates our socioeconomic situation and Nepal's business potential. Despite the fact that the country loses many prospective entrepreneurs every day, the number of remittances inflows is hailed as a tremendous achievement. However, entrepreneurship is becoming more popular, and young people are becoming more involved. Graduated youth are putting their skills and knowledge to use in their chosen fields. Youths are successfully running their own businesses by utilizing information technology and latest tools and equipment. They promote local products, explore them, and create new markets by identifying problems and providing solutions to those problems. As an agricultural country, youths are becoming more interested in agriculture, and they are doing well in this sector. As a result, Nepal has become self-sufficient in eggs, chicken and a variety of other agricultural products. Poultry, animal husbandry, fish farming, beekeeping, vegetable farming, and many other areas are being extensively explored. Other service and tourism industries are also being explored. Recently, online business has grown rapidly, despite the fact that the covid pandemic affects most industries, the online business thrives during this time.

Importance of startup businesses in entrepreneurship development

Startup businesses are important for the development of entrepreneurship because they are major factors for job creation and economic growth. Entrepreneurship is the process of launching and establishing a new business venture, and startup companies serve as the vehicles for bringing new ideas, products, and services to market. The importance of startup businesses in the development of entrepreneurship can be seen in several ways, such as the introduction of innovation, which aids in the development of entrepreneurship. Startup companies frequently bring to market new and innovative products and services, which can disrupt existing industries and drive economic growth. These companies are frequently founded by people who are passionate about a particular idea or product and have the drive and determination to make their vision a reality. Startup Businesses plays an important role in job creation. It also allow entrepreneurs and other workers to create their own jobs rather than relying on someone else for employment. Startup businesses can help to increase competition in a variety of industries and markets, resulting in affordable prices and higher quality for consumers. This increased competition can also drive innovation and open up new doors for entrepreneurs. Startup businesses contribute significantly to economic growth by developing new products and services and increasing competition in various industries. This has the potential to result in the creation of new jobs, increased productivity, and a more vibrant economy. In order to be successful, startup businesses require assistance from a variety of sources, including the government, investors, and business incubators. Governments can help startups by providing funding, tax breaks, and other incentives, while investors can provide the capital needed to get a business off the ground. In order to help startups succeed, business incubators provide mentorship, networking opportunities, and office space. Entrepreneurs who are willing to take calculated risks in order to bring their ideas to market are often associated with startup businesses. This willingness to take risks can drive innovation and open up new opportunities for entrepreneurs, as well as inspire others to start their own businesses. It can also help to increase diversity in various industries by bringing entrepreneurs from various backgrounds and experiences to the market with their unique perspectives and ideas. Increased diversity can lead to increased innovation and competitiveness. To summarize, startup businesses are critical to the development of entrepreneurship because they

drive innovation, job creation, competition, economic growth, and provide support networks for entrepreneurs. They also encourage risk-taking and diversity across industries, which can result in a more vibrant and dynamic economy.

Background

In the 20th century the theorist Arthur H. Cole defined an entrepreneur as an “organization builder”. The term entrepreneur is a French word, and is derived from the French word “*entreprendre*”. It means ‘to undertake’. It is commonly used to describe an individual who organizes and operates a business or businesses, taking on financial risk to do so. Around 1700 A.D. the term was used for architects and contractor of public works. In many countries, the term entrepreneur is often associated with a person who starts his/her own new business. Entrepreneurship is the process of creating, launching, and running a new business venture with the goal of creating value for customers and profit for the founders. It entails recognizing an opportunity, taking calculated risks, and being creative in the pursuit of creating something new. Entrepreneurs frequently bring a unique perspective to the market and drive change through their ideas and initiatives. In contrast, a startup business is a new and relatively young company that is attempting to grow and establish itself in the market. Startups are typically innovative, fast-paced, and adaptable, with the goal of disrupting existing industries or creating new markets. Startups typically have limited resources and must overcome numerous challenges, such as obtaining funding, assembling a team, developing and marketing products, and establishing a customer base. They do, however, have the potential to grow quickly and achieve significant success. Entrepreneurship often starts with spotting a market niche or a chance to start something new. The next step for entrepreneurs is to carry out market research to confirm their concept and ascertain whether there is a market for their good or service. They create a business strategy as well, including their vision, objectives, and plans for success. This plan comprises information on the business's structure, revenue-generating methods, and resource requirements. After establishing the entrepreneurial process, the next step is to secure funding for the business. This can be accomplished through a variety of means, such as obtaining bank loans, receiving investment from venture capital firms, or crowd funding. Entrepreneurs must understand their funding options and make informed decisions about how to finance their business. Another important aspect of entrepreneurship and startup businesses is team building. Entrepreneurs must surround themselves with people who possess the skills and knowledge that they lack, such as marketing, sales, and technical knowledge. A strong and supportive team can help a startup overcome many of the challenges it will face, and can make or break the business's success. Once the company is up and running, entrepreneurs must concentrate on providing value to their customers. This includes creating and marketing products or services that meet the needs of their customers and solving problems for them. Entrepreneurs must also be innovative in their approach to sales and marketing in order to reach and engage their target audience. As a startup grows and changes, there will be a lot of trial and error in the early phases. Entrepreneurs must be adaptable and flexible, and they must be prepared to change their approach when necessary. They must also maintain their attention on their objectives and avoid getting sidetracked by the numerous obstacles they will encounter. Finally, it's important to remember that starting a business and becoming an entrepreneur both include some risk. There is no assurance that a startup will succeed, and many do. The benefits of entrepreneurship, however, can be tremendous, and many prosperous businesspeople go on to experience great success and have a big impact on the world. To summarize, entrepreneurship and startup businesses involve taking calculated risks, being innovative, and creating something new that adds value to the market. Entrepreneurs must have a clear vision, a well-thought-out plan, and the will to succeed. While there will be many challenges along the way, the rewards of entrepreneurship and startup businesses can be substantial, both financially and personally.

Historical Background of entrepreneurship in Nepal

Since the pre-modern era, there has been a long and rich history of entrepreneurship in Nepal. People worked in agriculture, handicrafts, and trade in Nepal, a nation with small-scale and cottage industries. These traditional enterprises, which were run by families and passed down from one generation to the next, were a major part of the Nepalese economy. Nepal underwent a phase of modernization and commercialization under the Rana reign (1846–1951). The Ranas developed a centralized government and imported Western innovations and ideas. During this time, trade and commerce expanded along with the rise of merchant capitalism. The Ranas promoted entrepreneurship by authorizing a small number of people to start firms and by promoting private investment across a range of economic sectors. However, the Rana era was characterized by a lack of competition and a closed economy, which limited entrepreneurship. The Ranas also established strict regulations, which made it difficult for small businesses to compete with large corporations. This era saw a decline in the traditional cottage industries, and a shift towards large-scale industries, such as textiles and manufacturing. Nepal experienced significant political and economic changes following the fall of the Rana regime. The 1950s saw the emergence of democracy and the adoption of a new constitution that granted citizens greater rights and liberties. The 1960s saw the establishment of a mixed economy, with both the private and public sectors contributing to the country's development. In the 1960s and 1970s, the establishment of private sector industries such as pharmaceuticals and food processing signaled the beginning of a new era of entrepreneurship in Nepal. The Nepalese economy underwent significant liberalization and privatization reforms in the 1990s. Many small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) were established during this time period, and they played an important role in the economy's growth. As the government implemented favorable policies, such as tax breaks, and provided assistance to SMEs through various programs and schemes, entrepreneurship became more accessible. Entrepreneurship in Nepal has grown in recent years, particularly in the information technology (IT) and service sectors. The advancement of technology and the internet has created new opportunities for entrepreneurs and made it easier for Nepalese businesses to reach a larger market. Furthermore, the government has established a number of programs and initiatives to encourage entrepreneurship, such as the creation of incubation centers and the provision of financing and mentorship programs.

Finally, traditional commerce and companies have been the main forms of entrepreneurship in Nepal for many years. However, it wasn't until the second half of the 20th century that entrepreneurship in Nepal began to receive institutional recognition as an engine for economic growth and development. Since that time, the government of Nepal has been attempting to encourage entrepreneurship through programs including the creation of entrepreneurship development centers and the provision of training and financial possibilities to would-be business owners. Despite obstacles such as a lack of capital and infrastructure, more young people are beginning their own businesses, which has led to an increase in entrepreneurship in Nepal.

Overview of current entrepreneurship landscape in Nepal

Entrepreneurship is currently growing and developing in Nepal, with an increasing number of young people starting their own businesses. Despite challenges such as a lack of infrastructure and funding, entrepreneurship has been identified as a key driver of Nepal's economic growth and development. The Nepalese government has launched a number of initiatives to encourage entrepreneurship in the country, including the establishment of entrepreneurship development centers and the provision of training and funding opportunities for aspiring entrepreneurs. National Innovation centre is established under the leadership of young scientist and social engineer Dr. Mahabir Pun. The National Innovation Center (NIC) Nepal offers a distinctive platform to assist in retaining innovative, talented, and passionate human capital of Nepal and leverage their brainpower and creativity in fostering the nation's social and economic development through motivated thought and effort.

National innovation centre seeks creative minds across the country and provide them a platform where they can launch new approaches, concepts, or products in order to advance the national progress.

In recent years, the number of startups and small businesses in Nepal has increased significantly, particularly in sectors such as technology, tourism, and agriculture. The rise of Nepal's tech industry has been particularly notable, with an increasing number of Nepalese entrepreneurs launching startups in software development, digital marketing, and e-commerce. The rise of tech startups is one of the major trends in Nepal's entrepreneurship ecosystem. Many young Nepalese entrepreneurs are using their technical skills to develop innovative solutions to local problems in fields such as e-commerce, fintech, and education technology. Some well-known Nepalese startups include Tootle, Pathao, ESewa, a digital wallet, Ultima lifestyle, Home glory, Edulink, Baltra (which is also expanded in India). According to data from the fiscal year 2074/75 there was around 275433 registered SMEs in Nepal. Also, According to Industrial Act 2016, any business having capital up to Rs 100 million is categorized as a small enterprise whereas a business having fixed capital between Rs 100 million to Rs 250 million is categorized as a medium enterprise And, According to World Bank's- Doing Business Survey, Nepal ranks 135 out of 190 for starting a business. This demonstrates how miserable enterprises are in Nepal. In conclusion, the government's favorable policies, the country's expanding youth population, and more access to technology are all contributing to Nepal's entrepreneurial landscape's rapid evolution. Even if there are still difficulties, Nepalese business owners have a bright future as long as they keep coming up with original solutions to local problems.

The Effect of Startup Business on Entrepreneurial and Economic Development

A. Increase job opportunities and economic growth

Startups are creative small firms with a focus on quick expansion. The startup business has grown rapidly over the last few decades and has emerged as a key force in the creation of both jobs and the economy. In many nations, startups are seen as essential to fostering entrepreneurial growth and the next wave of successful entrepreneurs. The creation of job opportunities is one of the most significant effects of startup businesses on entrepreneurial development. Startups are well-known for their ability to generate new job opportunities, particularly in the technology and software industries. This is due to the fact that startups are frequently focused on developing new products and services to address unmet market needs. These new products and services result in the creation of new jobs, which can benefit the local economy. Furthermore, startups are frequently more adaptable and flexible than larger corporations, which can lead to more job opportunities as the company grows and expands.

B. Encouragement of innovation and creativity

Another significant impact of startups on entrepreneurial development is the encouragement of innovation. Startups are frequently at the cutting edge of innovation, constantly experimenting with new ideas, products, and business models. This constant experimentation has the potential to lead to the development of new technologies, products, and services with the potential to change the world. This innovation has the potential to generate new industries and job opportunities, thereby driving economic growth and development.

C. Improve access to financing and resources

Startups are essential for enhancing businesses' access to resources and financing. Startups contribute to the ecosystem of the entrepreneurial economy by fostering new enterprises and innovation. The success of startups acts as a proof of concept, motivating them to pursue their own companies. By offering networking opportunities, mentorship, and access to capital and other resources, startups also contribute to the development of supportive ecosystems. As a result, an environment is created that encourages and supports the establishment of new firms, innovation and economic progress. In this way, startups are essential to enhancing resources and finance for entrepreneurship growth.

D. Development of entrepreneurial ecosystem

The startup ecosystem is also important in developing the next generation of entrepreneurs. Startups frequently provide a nurturing environment in which entrepreneurs can learn, grow, and develop their skills. Many startups are founded by first-time entrepreneurs who are willing to take a risk in order to pursue their passion. These entrepreneurs will have the opportunity to learn from experienced mentors, network with other entrepreneurs, and gain valuable hands-on business experience. This environment can help to nurture the next generation of successful entrepreneurs.

Furthermore, the success of startups can have a positive impact on the local community and the economy as a whole. Startups with significant growth and success can create new industries and job opportunities, as well as transfer knowledge and skills to other businesses and entrepreneurs. The success of a startup can also result in the formation of spinoff businesses, as employees leave to start their own businesses, which can contribute to the growth of the local ecosystem. It is crucial to remember that not all startups succeed and that many will fail. This is a typical stage in the entrepreneurial process and is frequently considered as a chance for business owners to improve their operations and learn from their failures. Due to the significant lessons learnt and the development of new goods and services, the failure of a startup can also result in the creation of new business prospects for future entrepreneurs. In conclusion, startups have a significant influence on the growth of the entrepreneurial sector. They foster innovation, create job opportunities, and offer an encouraging atmosphere for entrepreneurs to develop. The local community and the national economy may benefit from the success of startups. Even if not all businesses are successful, a startup's failure can nevertheless offer entrepreneurs useful lessons and aid in the growth of the neighborhood ecosystem.

Challenges Faced by startup businesses in Nepal

Start-ups are considered drivers of the economy (Jonek-Kowalska & Wolniak, 2021). The number of start-ups has increased by roughly 20 times in less than ten years (Lyons & Zhang, 2017; Nafukho & Muya, 2010). Following the international trend, the culture of entrepreneurship and start-ups has slowly been evolving in Nepal within the last decade. Many millennials have also entered the entrepreneurial ecosystem by launching new start-ups. Recently Nepal has been identified as one of the least developed countries (LDC) in the world (United Nations "List of least," 2021). As a developing country, the challenges that Nepali start-ups face are likely similar to those of other developing countries because of similar political and economic conditions. One of the most difficult challenges for Nepalese startups is obtaining sufficient funding. Many startups face difficulties obtaining loans or investment from banks, financial institutions, or venture capital firms. This lack of funding frequently limits these businesses' growth potential because they are unable to invest in the resources required to expand. Reaching out to potential customers can be difficult for Nepalese startups due to limited market access, due to a lack of infrastructure and low consumer purchasing power which makes difficult for businesses to expand and reach a large number of customers. With limited access to transportation, energy, and communication, Nepal's infrastructure is insufficient to meet the needs of many enterprises. This can make it challenging for startups to function effectively and efficiently, which can impede their growth. Another significant issue for companies in Nepal is a lack of skilled workers. Due to the absence of a strong education and training system, it might be challenging to find the talent needed to develop and flourish. Due to bureaucratic hurdles and a complex regulatory environment, starting and running a business in Nepal can be complicated and time consuming. Many talented and qualified Nepalese leave the nation to pursue better prospects in other countries, making it challenging for startups to locate and keep skilled staff.

This can make it difficult for startups to navigate the system and maintain regulatory, because the Nepalese market is small and has limited resources. It is difficult for startups to compete with established businesses and larger corporations. This can be especially difficult for companies looking to enter the new markets or establish themselves in existing ones. In Nepal, attitudes toward entrepreneurship and risk-taking can be conservative, making it difficult for new businesses to gain traction. This can also make it difficult for entrepreneurs to obtain the necessary support

from friends, family, and the larger community. Obtaining necessary permits and licenses can also be difficult for Nepalese entrepreneurs. The process can be complex and time-consuming, and small businesses may struggle to navigate the bureaucracy and various regulations. This can cause delays in launching or expanding a business, negatively impacting its success. Despite these obstacles, there are numerous opportunities for startups to succeed in Nepal. With a growing economy, rising consumer purchasing power, and a growing interest in entrepreneurship, the country has the potential for businesses to succeed. Startups that can overcome obstacles and capitalize on available opportunities can have a significant impact in Nepal and beyond. To summarize, startups in Nepal face numerous challenges, but with perseverance and a willingness to adapt to the country's unique conditions, there is potential for success. By addressing the challenges and capitalizing on the opportunities, startups can help drive economic growth and improve people's lives in Nepal.

Conclusion

In recent years, new enterprises have had a big impact on Nepal's entrepreneurial growth. Young entrepreneurs eager to launch their own businesses and motivated by a desire to generate employment and improve their communities are becoming more prevalent across the nation. The government has also started a number of measures to help support new enterprises because it recognizes the potential of entrepreneurship as an engine for economic growth. The creation of jobs has been one of the main ways that new enterprises have influenced the growth of the entrepreneurial sector in Nepal. Startups are viewed as a means of creating new job possibilities and lowering unemployment, which is a significant issue in the nation. In addition, by bringing fresh goods and services to the market, entrepreneurs support economic diversification and innovation. Another significant impact of startup companies is the creation of a supportive ecosystem for entrepreneurs. Access to funding, mentorship, training, and networking opportunities are all part of this. The government has played an important role in this by launching initiatives like the Nepal Startup Fund, which provides seed funding to early-stage startups, and the Nepal Entrepreneurs' Hub, which serves as a platform for entrepreneurs to connect and collaborate. The expansion of startups has also been beneficial for Nepal's general business climate. This involves enhancing the ease of conducting business, expanding financial access, and strengthening intellectual property rights protection. These elements have a significant role in attracting more foreign investment into the nation, which supports economic expansion and expands business opportunities. Nevertheless, despite the benefits of startups, Nepali entrepreneurs continue to face a number of difficulties. This includes a shortage of competent talent, weak infrastructure, and restricted access to financing. If the government and other stakeholders want to see sustained growth in the startup sector and continue to encourage the expansion of entrepreneurship in the nation, they must solve these issues. In conclusion, there has been a considerable and positive impact of new enterprises on the growth of entrepreneurship in Nepal. The nation has experienced job creation, the construction of an ecosystem that supports entrepreneurs, and improvements to the general business climate. However, in order to maintain the growth of startups and encourage the development of entrepreneurship in the nation, issues like insufficient infrastructure and limited access to capital must be addressed.

Recommendations for improving the startup ecosystem in Nepal

Although there are many obstacles that need to be overcome in order to strengthen the startup ecosystem, Nepal has a great deal of potential to become a center for innovation and entrepreneurship. By getting government assistance, by offering financial assistance, tax breaks, and a supportive regulatory environment, the government can play a significant role in fostering entrepreneurship. The government can also be of assistance by setting up a central location where business owners can access information and tools and by encouraging the growth of business incubators and accelerators. Entrepreneurs may convert their ideas into profitable businesses with the aid of entrepreneurship

education, access to the relevant skills, and training. This can be accomplished by providing funding to educational institutions, as well as workshops and training programs for aspiring business owners. Nepal must promote an innovative culture where business owners are praised and supported. This can be accomplished by planning occasions and activities that highlight the achievements of regional businesspeople as well as by giving them chances to connect and work together. Early-stage investment is critical for startup success, but it can be difficult for Nepalese entrepreneurs to access the capital they require to grow. The government can help improve access to capital by fostering a thriving venture capital market and encouraging angel investing. The government should create a legal environment that encourages entrepreneurship, protects intellectual property, and level the playing field for startups. This can be accomplished by streamlining business registration processes, improving contract enforcement mechanisms, and making dispute resolution mechanisms more accessible. Startups can benefit from using the resources and experience they need to flourish through partnerships with established businesses, other organizations, and other groups. The government can promote entrepreneurship in the private sector and offer incentives for businesses to invest in startups in order to promote these collaborations. Startups can develop and prosper if they are encouraged to enter domestic and worldwide markets through trade shows, exhibits, and other events. By supporting trade promotion initiatives and encouraging entrepreneurship in the export industry, the government can aid in promoting access to markets. The success of startups depends on having a solid technological foundation and having access to data, technology, and other resources. The government can contribute to infrastructure improvement by making investments in broadband and technology infrastructure and by facilitating access to technology and data resources.

In conclusion, strengthening Nepal's startup ecosystem will necessitate a multifaceted strategy that includes support from the government, the development of human capital, a culture of innovation, access to funding, a favorable legal climate, partnerships with the private sector, access to markets, and infrastructure development. By overcoming these obstacles, Nepal may realize its enormous potential and establish itself as a center for innovation and business.

Final thoughts on the future of entrepreneurship in Nepal

Over the past ten years, Nepal has seen a sharp increase in entrepreneurship. Despite a number of obstacles, Nepal's future for business appears bright. Political stability, a growing market economy, and rising foreign investment are a few of the main elements that are anticipated to support the expansion of entrepreneurship in the nation. Nepal government should minimize corruption and provide a favorable climate for private sector investment, including policies that promote corporate growth and attract international investment because both are essential for economic progress. Nepal's tourism which features some of the world's most stunning landscapes and cultural sites, to meet the growing demand for tourism, startups might provide unique travel experiences, tour packages, or travel-tech solutions. Nepal has a rich cultural heritage, which is a valuable resource that may be used to boost tourism and the country's economy. When promoting Nepal's tourism potential, the government should safeguard and preserve the country's cultural legacy. Nepal can foster regional cooperation because Nepal is physically placed between two of the world's largest and fastest-growing economies, India and China. Regional cooperation can assist Nepal in capitalizing on its advantageous location and reaping the benefits of economic integration with its neighbors. Nepal also has enormous renewable energy potential, and entrepreneurs might focus on developing solutions in sectors such as solar power, hydro power, or wind power. Startups could also create solutions in fields like recycling, waste reduction, or waste-to-energy conversion to address Nepal's enormous waste management concerns.

Another important element that is anticipated to fuel the expansion of entrepreneurship in Nepal is the increasing number of young people in the country. New entrepreneurs are emerging as a result of young people looking for new chances to launch their own enterprises and create jobs. Furthermore, the increasing availability of low-cost technology, such as Smartphone's, laptop computers, and internet access, has made it easier for entrepreneurs to start

and run their businesses. To summarize, the future of entrepreneurship in Nepal appears bright, but there are still several challenges that must be addressed before it can reach its full potential. The government, private sector, and other organizations must collaborate to create a welcoming environment for entrepreneurs by addressing issues such as access to finance, infrastructure, and the legal and regulatory framework. Entrepreneurship has the potential to drive economic growth and create new opportunities for Nepalese youth with the right support and environment.

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References

- [1] Rijal S, 2021. The five biggest factors challenging startups in Nepal, Vol. 5/1., 64-72
- [2] Esabda. (2022, January 6). *Entrepreneurship Development In Nepal | Difficulties, And Opportunities*. Esabda. <https://esabda.com/entrepreneurship-development-in-nepal-difficulties-and-opportunities/>
- [3] Pandey, L. (2020, October 3). *Entrepreneurship In Nepal | Scholar Nepal :: Digital Journal*. Scholarnepal.com. <https://scholarnepal.com/article/title/78-entrepreneurship-in-nepal>
- [4] Taxmann. (2021, September 8). *Entrepreneurship - Concept, Functions, Need and Its relevance in Indian Society*. Taxmann Blog. <https://www.taxmann.com/post/blog/entrepreneurship-concept-functions-need-and-its-relevance-in-indian-society?amp>
- [5] Uniglobe. (2019, May 23). *JOURNEY OF NEPALI ENTREPRENEURSHIP*. UNIGLOBE COLLEGE. <https://uniglobe.edu.np/journey-of-nepali-entrepreneurship/>